

Knowledge, attitude, and practices towards hand hygiene among in-school adolescents in a metropolitan city in Nigeria

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Abstract

Introduction: We assessed the knowledge and practices towards hand hygiene among in-school adolescents in Ibadan, Nigeria.

Methods: This cross-sectional study was conducted among 394 in-school adolescents. Hand hygiene knowledge was assessed with 29 questions, and practices were assessed using 24 questions. Adolescents with scores ≥ 18 points were said to have good knowledge of hand hygiene, while those with scores ≥ 16 points observed good hand hygiene practices. Data analyses were conducted at univariate, bivariate, and multivariate levels ($\alpha 0.05$).

Results: Adolescents' mean age was 13.7 ± 2.0 years, and 232 (58.9%) attended public schools. Overall, 230 (58.4%) adolescents had good knowledge of hand hygiene; 118 (72.8%) in the private and 103 (44.4%) in the public schools, while 288 (73.1%) in-school adolescents observed good hand hygiene practices; 132 (81.5%) in the private and 156 (67.2%) in the public schools. Overall, 122 (55.6%) adolescents attending public schools had good hand hygiene knowledge ($\chi^2 = 7.78$, $p=0.005$). Also, 156 (67.2%) adolescents in public schools observed good practices ($\chi^2=9.84$, $p=0.002$). There was two times odds of good knowledge (aOR=1.94, $p=0.003$) and good hand hygiene practices (aOR=2.41, $p=0.001$) among adolescents in private schools.

Conclusions: Improving hand hygiene practices requires building hygiene infrastructure and implementing educational initiatives to promote sustained behavioral change in school environments.

Take-home message: Hand hygiene promotion interventions are one of the core aspects of health education in schools. Improving hand hygiene practices requires building hygiene infrastructure and implementing educational initiatives to promote sustained behavioral change in school environments.

Keywords: adolescents; behavior change; hand hygiene; health education; school health.

INTRODUCTION

Hand hygiene is a crucial public health strategy, particularly among in-school adolescents, to mitigate the spread of infectious diseases [1]. As emphasized by Opara and Alex-Hart [3], it is a key recommendation for infection control, especially during pandemics like COVID-19. Creating an enabling environment for hand hygiene in schools holds significant potential to reshape students' behavioral patterns, fostering improved hygiene practices within the school premises and extending to their homes and communities at large [3]. The vulnerability of adolescents to infectious diseases is heightened by their energetic and contact-intensive activities at school, exposing them to various pathogens [4]. Instilling enduring healthy habits during childhood and adolescence is paramount, given their susceptibility to infections originating from unwashed hands.

Hygiene promotion, identified by the World Bank [5] as the most cost-effective health intervention, plays a pivotal role in disease prevention. Good hand hygiene practices within communities have been shown to reduce the incidence of diarrhea by 23-40% and respiratory infections by about 21% [6,7]. Notably, a randomized control trial revealed that regular hand hygiene with soap and water significantly decreased the incidence of diarrhea and impetigo by over 50% among children, with a similar reduction observed in pneumonia cases [8]. This underscores the significance of providing basic hygiene services in institutions such as schools, hospitals, and workplaces to curb the transmission of diseases [9,10].

Examining hand hygiene practices among in-school adolescents, a study in Lagos State, Nigeria, reported that 84.3% of students wash their hands at school [4]. Further investigation revealed varied hand hygiene moments, with percentages as follows: after cleaning the school environment (3.1%), after break time (10.5%), before eating (40.2%), and after using the toilet (42.2%). However, less than half of the respondents (47.3%) reported washing hands with soap and water at school [4]. In Abia State, Nigeria, another survey disclosed that despite 78.7% of secondary school students possessing good knowledge, only about 35% exhibited good handwashing practices, primarily due to insufficient handwashing facilities [11].

Understanding the diffusion of innovation theory [12] is crucial in interpreting how hand-hygiene messages and knowledge are perceived as innovations beneficial to individuals. The theory also sheds light on the attitudes and norms influencing the intent to adopt this innovation. By comprehending these factors, interventions can be tailored to effectively promote good hand hygiene practices, considering the diverse types of adopters involved in the process. Access to basic hygiene services goes beyond the home setting, as a reasonable amount of time is spent outside. Students spend a significant portion of their childhood at school. Therefore, basic hygiene services must be provided in educational institutions to reduce the risk of disease transmission [9]. Many schools in Southwest Nigeria are not well positioned to cope with the hand-hygiene protocols required for curtailing the spread of diseases, with evidence showing that many still have poor perceptions about disease preventive measures such as hand hygiene [13]. This study aimed to determine the knowledge and practices towards hand hygiene among in-school adolescents in a metropolitan city in Nigeria.

METHODS

Study design and population target

This descriptive cross-sectional study was conducted in Ibadan, the capital city of Oyo State. Ibadan has a very rich cultural heritage and is noted to be the city of many firsts- The first university in Nigeria (University of Ibadan), the first teaching hospital in Nigeria (University College Hospital), the first television station (Nigeria Television Authority, Ibadan Network Centre) in Nigeria, etc. However, despite the reputation of the many firsts in Nigeria, Ibadan has been identified as one of the dirtiest cities in Nigeria [14]. Ibadan has over 100 public and private high (secondary schools) distributed across 11 local government areas. Ibadan Southwest is one of the urban and most developed local government areas in Ibadan metropolis, and schools in this area are expected to observe good hygiene practices.

The study site included private and public secondary schools in Ibadan Southwest local government area, Ibadan, Oyo State.

The study population comprised in-school adolescents currently enrolled in all six high school classes. The current education system in Nigeria is 9-3-4, called Universal Basic Education (U.B.E.). The U.B.E. implies that every child spends the first 9-years of primary or elementary (first 6 years) and compulsory education (the next three years) up to the junior secondary (high) school (JSS-3) level, another 3 years in the senior secondary (high) school, and 4-years in the tertiary institution [15]. The average age of enrolment in high school is 10 years, while the average age of exit from the same is 16 years.

Sampling procedure and study instruments

We utilized the sample size formula for a single proportion to estimate the number of respondents. A standard Z-score corresponding to a 95% confidence interval, the proportion of students who possessed good knowledge of handwashing practices was placed at 83%⁴, and an allowable sampling error of 4% was used. After adjusting for a 10% non-response rate, the minimum sample size was approximated 400.

Using a four-stage sampling technique we divided Ibadan Southwest local government area into four political wards, each containing at least eight schools. We adopted a simple random sampling technique, two wards were selected, out of which four schools were chosen. Next, we stratified each enrolled school into arms. This was followed by a systematic random selection of respondents from each stratum.

An electronic data collection tool, *Epicollect*, was designed and used to collect data from the student. The questionnaire had three sections and elicited information on respondents' background characteristics (age, current class, religion, sex, and parent's level of education), knowledge of hand hygiene, and hand hygiene practices. Hand hygiene knowledge was assessed with 29 questions, with one mark assigned to each correct answer. Hand hygiene practices were evaluated using 24 questions, with one mark assigned to each correct answer. We also used an observation checklist to determine the availability of hand hygiene facilities in each school.

We conducted content and face validity from experts in the field of public health. Construct validity was also ensured, so that variables in the objectives were well represented in the instrument. The drafted questionnaire was pretested among 15% of the study population in another similar local government area in Oyo State. The retrieved filled pretested questionnaire was subjected to Cronbach alpha analysis, and we obtained a reliability coefficient of 0.723. The feedback from the pilot study was used to strengthen the data collection tools.

Statistical analysis

Data were managed at the back end by an administrator to ensure accuracy. Afterward, the dataset was downloaded, cleaned, and imported into SPSS, where it was analyzed. The total obtainable knowledge score was 29 points. The mean knowledge score (18 points) was used as a cut-off. In-school adolescents with scores ≥ 18 points were said to have good knowledge of hand hygiene, while those with scores < 18 points were defined as having poor knowledge of hand hygiene. The total obtainable practice score was 24 points. The mean practice score (16 points) was used as a cut-off. In-school adolescents with scores ≥ 16 points were said to observe good hand hygiene practices, while those with scores < 16 points were defined as having poor hand hygiene practices.

Analysis was conducted at univariate, bivariate (Chi-square and Correlation tests) and multivariate levels. All variables were pooled into the first logistic regression model to determine the factors associated with good knowledge, positive attitude, and good practices toward hand hygiene. Variables significant at 10% in the first model were then pooled into the second model to determine the true predictors of good knowledge, positive attitude, and good practices towards hand hygiene. The

data collected using the observation checklist were analyzed in line with the study objectives. The data sets were kept electronically in a locked Computer for privacy.

Ethical aspects

The study was conducted in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki and approved by the Ethics Committee of Oyo State Ministry of Health Research Ethics Committee (Reference No: AD 13/479/2113A and date of approval: 24th January 2022). The purpose of the research was first explained to the school authority, represented by the principal, vice-principal, and senior teacher in some schools, to gain their consent for questionnaire administration and observation of the school regarding the availability and use of hand hygiene facilities. Afterward, the students were approached, and the purpose of the research was explained to them to gain their assent (for those less than 18 years) and consent (for those more than 18 years). The study participants were not coerced into joining the study. They were informed that they had the choice to partake even though the school authorities permitted us to conduct the study. They were informed that they could also decide to withdraw at any point during the study. No harm was inflicted on anyone because of their participation.

RESULTS

Overall, 394 interviews were conducted, thereby generating a response rate of 98.5%. The mean age of the respondents was 13.7 ± 2.0 years; 106 (26.9%) were below 13 years, and 212 (53.8%) were aged 13-15 years. Two hundred and twenty-five (57.1%) in-school adolescents were males, and 232 (58.9%) were currently enrolled in public school. (Table 1).

Table 1. Sociodemographic characteristics of adolescents enrolled from selected schools in Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria, 2021.

Characteristics	Frequency	%
Sex		
Male	225	57.1
Female	169	42.9
Age (Years)		
<13	106	26.9
13-15	212	53.8
>15	76	19.3
School type		
Public	232	58.9
Private	162	41.1
Class category		
Junior	163	41.4
Senior	231	58.6
Religion		
Christianity	240	60.9
Islam	154	39.1
Father's level of education		
Secondary and below	147	37.3
Tertiary	128	32.5
Postgraduate	119	30.2
Mother's level of education		
Secondary and below	155	39.3

Tertiary	135	34.3
Postgraduate	104	26.4

Overall, 230 (58.4%) in-school adolescents had good knowledge of hand hygiene; 118 (72.8%) in private and 103 (44.4%) in the public school. A total of 288 (73.1%) in-school adolescents observed good hand hygiene practices; 132 (81.5%) in private and 156 (67.2%) in the public school (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Knowledge and practices towards hand hygiene among in-school adolescents in Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria.

Figure 2 describes the sources of information on hand hygiene. A total of 238 (60.4%) in-school adolescents learnt about hand hygiene from social media, 214 (54.4%) utilized television, 203 (51.4%) learnt from school/teachers, while 183 (46.4%) were taught hand hygiene in the home environment by their parents.

Figure 2. Sources of information on hand hygiene among in-school adolescents in Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria (multiple responses).

Concerning hand hygiene practices in the school environment, 314 (79.7%) washed their hands after urinating, 334 (85.4%) washed their hands after defecation, 318 (80.7%) washed their hands after emptying the garbage, 344 (94.0%) dried their hands with napkins after washing them, 228 (62.3%) avoided biting their fingernails, and 226 (57.4%) avoided handshaking with peers. Overall, 337 (85.5%) adolescents preferred washing their hands with either water only or soap and water based on availability.

During a walk-through survey using a checklist, we found that boreholes and wells were the sources of water in the majority of the school. Schools (especially the public) that lacked boreholes and wells resorted to engaging their adolescents to fetch water from wells and boreholes near the school premises. Handwashing stations were frequently mounted close to the school entrance or near the toilet in schools where they were present and managed by either the domestic staff, school prefects, or teachers. Soap and water were sometimes available at the handwashing stations, but hand sanitizers were not available at all. In most schools, the handwashing stations comprised either a veronica bucket and a receptacle or ceramic basins fixed with tap and running water.

From Table 2, a total of 60 (56.6%) adolescents aged below 13 years had good knowledge of hand hygiene compared to 130 (61.3%) aged 13-15 years and 40 (52.6%) aged above 15 years ($\chi^2 = 1.93$, $p = 0.382$), and 122 (55.6%) adolescents attending public schools had good knowledge of hand hygiene compared to 108 (66.7%) attending private schools ($\chi^2 = 7.78$, $p = 0.005$).

Table 2. Factors associated with hand hygiene knowledge among in-school adolescents in Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria, 2021.

Characteristics	Knowledge of hand hygiene		Chi-square	p-value
	Good n (%)	Poor n (%)		
Sex				
Male	123 (54.7)	62 (36.7)	2.97	0.085
Female	107 (63.3)	102 (45.3)		
Age (Years)				
<13	60 (56.6)	46 (43.4)	1.93	0.382
13-15	130 (61.3)	82 (38.7)		
>15	40 (52.6)	36 (47.4)		
School type				
Public	122 (52.6)	110 (47.4)	7.78	0.005*
Private	108 (66.7)	54 (33.3)		
Class category				
Junior	82 (50.3)	81 (49.7)	7.45	0.006*
Senior	148 (64.1)	83 (35.9)		
Religion				
Christianity	141 (58.8)	99 (41.2)	0.04	0.851
Islam	89 (57.8)	65 (42.2)		
Father's level of education				
Secondary and below	79 (53.7)	68 (46.3)	2.58	0.276
Tertiary	81 (63.3)	47 (36.7)		
Postgraduate	70 (58.8)	49 (41.2)		
Mother's level of education				
Secondary and below	83 (53.5)	72 (46.5)	2.74	0.254
Tertiary	81 (60.0)	54 (40.0)		
Postgraduate	66 (63.5)	38 (36.5)		

Note: * $P < 0.05$

One hundred and seventy-six males (78.2%) had good hand hygiene practices compared to 112 (68.3%) females ($\chi^2 = 7.01$, $p = 0.002$). Also, 156 (67.2%) adolescents enrolled in public schools had good hand hygiene practices compared to 132 (81.5%) attending private schools ($\chi^2 = 9.84$, $p = 0.002$). Other factors influencing good hand hygiene practices among these in-school adolescents are shown in Table 3.

Table 3. Factors associated with hand hygiene practices among in-school adolescents in Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria, 2021.

Characteristics	Hand hygiene practices		Chi-square	p-value
	Good n (%)	Poor n (%)		
Sex				
Male	176 (78.2)	49 (21.8)	7.01	0.002*
Female	112 (68.3)	57 (33.7)		
Age (Years)				
<13	79 (74.5)	27 (22.5)	2.57	0.277
13-15	159 (75.0)	53 (25.0)		
>15	50 (65.8)	26 (34.2)		
School type				
Public	156 (67.2)	76 (32.8)	9.84	0.002*
Private	132 (81.5)	30 (18.5)		
Class category				
Junior	125 (76.7)	38 (23.3)	1.82	0.177
Senior	163 (70.6)	68 (29.4)		
Religion				
Christianity	171 (71.3)	69 (28.7)	1.07	0.302
Islam	117 (76.0)	37 (24.0)		
Father's level of education				
Secondary and below	112 (76.2)	35 (23.8)	15.52	<0.001*
Tertiary	78 (60.9)	50 (39.1)		
Postgraduate	98 (82.4)	21 (17.6)		
Mother's level of education				
Secondary and below	118 (76.1)	37 (23.9)	8.25	0.016*
Tertiary	87 (64.4)	38 (35.6)		
Postgraduate	83 (79.8)	21 (20.2)		
Knowledge of hand hygiene				
Good	170 (73.9)	60 (26.1)	0.19	0.665
Poor	118 (72.0)	46 (28.0)		

Note: * $P < 0.05$

Compared to in-school adolescents above 15 years, those below 13 had more than two times higher odds of good hand hygiene knowledge (aOR = 2.16, 95%CI = 0.98 – 4.77, $p = 0.058$). Compared to in-school adolescents above 15 years, those aged 13-15 years had approximately twice higher odds of good hand hygiene knowledge (aOR = 1.62, 95%CI = 0.93 – 2.82, $p = 0.092$). Adolescents enrolled in private schools had two times higher odds of good hand hygiene knowledge than those in public schools (aOR = 1.94, 95%CI = 1.21 – 3.10, $p = 0.003$) (Table 4).

Table 4. Predictors of good knowledge of hand hygiene among in-school adolescents in Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria, 2021.

	Model 1			Model 2		
	Unadjusted Odds Ratio	95% Confidence Interval	p-value	Adjusted Odds Ratio	95% Confidence interval	p-value
Sex						
Male	1					
Female	1.27	0.82 – 1.96	0.287			
Age (Years)						
<13	2.08	0.93 – 4.64	0.075	2.16	0.98 – 4.77	0.058
13-15	1.59	0.91 – 2.77	0.107	1.62	0.93 – 2.82	0.092
>15	1					
School type						
Public	1			1		
Private	1.93	1.20 – 3.09	0.007*	1.94	1.21 – 3.10	0.003*
Class category						
Junior	1			1		
Senior	2.58	1.43 - 2.64	0.002*	2.57	1.43 – 4.62	0.001*
Religion						
Christianity	1.05	0.66 - 1.67	0.828			
Islam	1					
Father's level of education						
Secondary and below	1.67	0.84 - 3.33	0.144	1.62	0.81 – 3.21	0.171
Tertiary	1.83	0.96 - 3.50	0.066**	1.92	0.95 – 3.46	0.069
Postgraduate	1					
Mother's level of education						
Secondary and below	1			1		
Tertiary	1.11	0.60 - 2.06	0.095**	0.56	0.28 – 1.11	0.095
Postgraduate	1.81	0.90 - 3.63	0.151	0.63	0.33 – 1.22	0.172
Knowledge of hand hygiene						
Good						
Poor						

Note: * $P < 0.05$, ** $P < 0.1$

From Table 5, female in-school adolescents had 46% less odds of good hand hygiene practices than their male peers (aOR = 0.46, 95%CI = 0.28 – 0.74, $p = 0.002$). Adolescents enrolled in private schools had more than two times higher odds of good hand hygiene practices than those in public schools (aOR = 2.41, 95%CI = 1.44 – 4.04, $p = 0.001$).

Table 5. Predictors of good hand hygiene practices among in-school adolescents in Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria, 2021.

	Model 1			Model 2		
	Unadjusted Odds Ratio	95% Confidence Interval	p-value	Adjusted Odds Ratio	95% Confidence interval	p-value
Sex						
Male	1			1		
Female	0.46	0.28 – 0.75	0.002*	0.46	0.28 – 0.74	0.002*
Age (Years)						
<13	0.93	0.37 – 2.31	0.826			
13-15	1.47	0.80 – 2.70	0.216			
>15	1					
School type						
Public	1			1		
Private	2.37	1.36 – 4.13	0.002	2.41	1.44 – 4.04	0.001*
Class category						
Junior	1					
Senior	0.70	0.35 - 1.40	0.314			
Religion						
Christianity	1.02	0.60 - 1.72	0.942			
Islam	1					
Father's level of education						
Secondary and below	0.67	0.30 - 1.52	0.340	0.73	0.39 – 1.37	0.329
Tertiary	0.39	0.19 - 0.81	0.012*	0.37	0.20 – 0.68	0.001*
Postgraduate						
Mother's level of education						
Secondary and below	1					
Tertiary	0.88	0.45 – 1.74	0.722			
Postgraduate	0.99	0.45 – 2.23	1.000			
Knowledge of hand hygiene						
Good	1.08	0.67 – 1.76	0.742			
Poor	1					

Note: *P< 0.05

DISCUSSION

This study aimed to determine the knowledge and practices towards hand hygiene among in-school adolescents in Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria. Our results revealed that more than half of the adolescents (58.4%) had good hand hygiene knowledge. The proportion observed in this study is lower than that reported from a cross-sectional study conducted among similar populations in Lagos State (83%)[4] and Abia State (78.7%), Nigeria [11], Saudi Arabia (80%) [16] and Sudan (65%)[17].

Although the level of good knowledge of hand hygiene was slightly about average, approximately three out of every four adolescents had good hand hygiene practices. These practices included trimming fingernails, avoiding face/eyes/nose touches and handshakes, and frequent hand washing and disinfection. This finding posits that adolescents do not understand the motivators for hand hygiene practices. They only adhere to these practices either in-home or school settings.

This may be attributed to insufficient emphasis on what hand hygiene entails and its benefits in reducing the frequency of occurrence of infectious diseases in educational and home settings. The respondents acknowledged the home and school environments as sources of information on hand hygiene. The synergy between home and school environments creates a comprehensive approach to disseminating information on hand hygiene [18]. This dual influence is crucial in fostering a holistic understanding and commitment to maintaining good hand hygiene practices, as these adolescents are consistently exposed to reinforcing messages and demonstrations in both settings. Adolescents likely receive information from parents, caregivers, or family members who serve as primary influencers within the home. These sources may include verbal communication, demonstrations, and proper handwashing techniques. The home environment is an intimate space where daily routines and habits are established, making it an influential setting for imbibing good hand hygiene practices [19].

In school settings, teachers and staff may conduct educational sessions, distribute informational materials, or display visual aids promoting proper hand hygiene. Additionally, schools have frequently implemented policies and practices, such as providing access to hand hygiene facilities and promoting regular handwashing breaks, contributing to the overall awareness and adoption of good hand hygiene practices [20].

In-school adolescents identified several factors hindering good hand hygiene practices, encompassing infrastructural and behavioral challenges. Issues such as poor water quality and inconsistent water supply pose significant barriers, as they directly impact the availability of essential resources for effective handwashing. The long distance to handwashing stations introduces an accessibility challenge, making it inconvenient for students to adhere to regular hygiene routines. Similar barriers have been reported in previous studies conducted in Nigeria [21,22].

An inadequate supply of hand sanitizers further compounds the problem, limiting alternative options for maintaining hand cleanliness. Additionally, forgetfulness emerged as a behavioral obstacle, indicating a need for strategies to enhance awareness and reinforce the importance of consistent hand hygiene practices among in-school adolescents. Enrolment in private school was a significant predictor of good knowledge and practices towards hand hygiene. Enrolment in private schools can potentially increase hand hygiene knowledge through several factors. Private schools often have better resources, infrastructure, including well-maintained and accessible hand hygiene facilities, and educational programs compared to some public institutions which can contribute to a more comprehensive learning environment [23]. Having convenient and well-equipped stations can encourage students to practice good hand hygiene consistently, especially adolescents in senior classes.

Compared to junior students, seniors may take on leadership roles within their class or groups. Assuming such responsibilities could involve educating and guiding junior students on the importance of hand hygiene, reinforcing their understanding in the process. Adolescents with fathers who have had postgraduate education demonstrated a lower level of knowledge of hand hygiene compared to those whose fathers had no postgraduate education. Adolescents with fathers who have had postgraduate education demonstrated better hand hygiene practices compared to those whose fathers had no postgraduate education. Fathers with postgraduate education should as well impact the knowledge of hand hygiene on their wards for them to also influence other children. This will lead to more translation of knowledge into good hand hygiene practices among adolescents.

Study limitations

This study was limited to the hand hygiene practices of adolescents in school environments. It did not cover their handwashing practices at home, where they spent substantial time. This study was also conducted among a representative

portion of in-school adolescents in Ibadan, Nigeria. It may not be generalizable for Nigeria's entire population of in-school adolescents.

CONCLUSIONS

Poor hand hygiene knowledge exists among in-school adolescents in Ibadan, Nigeria, especially those attending public schools. Hand hygiene practices are also poor among public school adolescents. Addressing this challenge requires a comprehensive approach that includes improving infrastructure, ensuring a stable supply of hygiene resources, and implementing educational initiatives to promote sustained behavioral change towards hand hygiene in school environments.

A randomized controlled trial could be undertaken to focus on developing and implementing targeted educational interventions to improve their understanding of proper hand hygiene practices.

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